

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE BUSINESS ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN AND ENSURING POPULATION EMPLOYMENT

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Annotation: one of the priorities with special attention in the economy is the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. Particular attention was paid to the implementation of structural changes in the national economy in accordance with the world market conjuncture, the development of new economic relations in the areas of production and service, the formation of a class of owners and, ultimately, the achievement of a decisive place for small business and entrepreneurship in increasing the standard of living of the population.

Keywords: small business, private enterprise, Employment, Network, economy

As our president stressed, the compact and mobility of small businesses, changes in market conjuncture and its rapid adaptation to consumer needs make it the most convenient and optimal tool in terms of creating new jobs and increasing population income in the context of global changes.

One of the main areas of activity carried out within the framework of the tasks set out in the "strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021", approved by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4947 of February 7, 2017 " creating a favorable business environment for the, focused on"strict prevention of illegal interventions by law enforcement and control agencies", during the period covered by the strategy, the sector and sectors of the economy, and at the same time small entrepreneurial activity in the cross section of the territories, were rapidly developed.[1]

The new Uzbekistan development strategy for 2022-2026 also clearly expresses strategic goals for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the form of "creating conditions for the organization of

entrepreneurial activity and the formation of permanent sources of income, bringing the share of the private sector in GDP to 80 percent and its share in exports to 60 percent".[2]

But, it should be noted that, although small business and private entrepreneurship are developing in the process of reforms carried out in our country, it is necessary to continuously continue scientific research on this type of activity, setting priorities for the development of the field and developing relevant practical proposals. Because small businesses, despite being economically independent, have the property of working in conditions of unparalleled competition. In addition, it makes it necessary to constantly focus on the issues of the availability of specific aspects and capabilities of the regions of our country in the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, their research, state regulation and support. At today's stage of Economic Development, Small Business and private enterprise in our country are considered one of the main factors of economic growth, and the main goal of economic reforms is the rapid development of sectors and sectors of the economy by creating a favorable environment for private entrepreneurship.

In our country, the change in the share of small entrepreneurship in the main macroeconomic indicators for the period 2011-2021 has certain fluctuations, these fluctuations can be explained by the content and essence of the reforms carried out at the country level.

In particular, during 2011-2018, it can be observed that all macroeconomic indicators of small business activity, including the volume of gross domestic product, the volume of industrial production, the volume of construction work, the level of employment, the share in the volume of exports and imports, have steadily increased. In particular, it is seen that the share of small-scale entrepreneurship in gross domestic product increased significantly during this period from 61.9% in 2011 to 62.4% in 2018, among other indicators. Since 2019, the share of small business activities in these indicators has been declining based on clear law (Table1).

The indicators for the share of small businesses in the country's main macroeconomic indicators over the past 11 years have had a trend of change based on clear law, as mentioned above. In the period after 2018, as a result of the development of large businesses in our country in parallel with small businesses, including the large growth of the volume of business entities, the share of small businesses in the main macroeconomic indicators has had a certain downward trend.

Table 1.

The main indicators of small business and private entrepreneurship in the sectors of the economy, billion. Soum[3]

Specification	Year										
	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Industry	13586,8	17114,6	23312,0	30907,0	39643,5	50654,5	61367,8	87962,0	83344,2	103020,8	121719,2
Construction	6188,3	7925,5	10377,7	13944,9	16954,0	19671,0	22469,4	37451,7	53960,9	63866,6	77762,0
Employment	8950,7	9239,7	9604,0	9950,8	10170,4	10397,5	10541,5	10128,8	10318,9	9865,7	10070,7
Exports (us \$ million)	2826,2	1910,5	3752,3	3657,8	3377,7	3139,2	2759,3	3810,8	4714,8	3100,9	3711,2
Import (US \$ Million)	3895,5	4946,0	5909,4	6352,6	5523,1	5676,8	7511,9	10916,2	14972,2	10943,3	12389,0
Trade	24741,9	32242,9	40564,5	50197,8	61972,3	78935,6	92973,0	114896,4	138920,7	164106,1	204787,4
Village, forest and fish farming	46704,5	56926,6	67510,7	82957,2	101197,5	118011,4	152010,5	191759,2	219466,9	253238,2	307280,2
Services	19556,5	24841,8	31409,1	40187,9	47269,6	61346,2	69212,7	84433,4	103106,6	114052,7	144812,7
Shipping (mln tn)	292,0	304,3	352,8	416,1	472,8	538,6	548,8	611,7	641,0	638,9	678,9
Cargo turnover (mln tn / km)	6894,3	7271,9	7919,1	8632,9	9225,1	10072,4	10444,4	11657,7	12152,3	12304,6	13108,1
Passenger transport (mln passenger)	3416,2	3687,9	3953,8	4224,5	4486,3	4866,5	5037,5	5242,6	5345,0	4904,8	5237,6
Passenger turnover (mln passenger / km)	74320,7	80210,0	86183,3	93024,7	99872,8	107789,7	111435,0	115335,2	117412,7	107766,7	114681,5

However even in quantitative terms, this suggests that it is incorrect to

conclude that the value of small business entities in the structure of macroeconomic indicators has decreased, since it can be seen that indicators in the dynamic range have grown quantitatively over the years.

The table data shows that the number of small business entities in the agrarian sector of the economy has grown more than 5 times over the past 9 years, that is, in 2013, 189867 units of small business entities operated on the network, while at the end of 2021 their number was 462834 units.

Table 2

Change in the share of small business activity in Uzbekistan in the main macroeconomic indicators, in %[3]

Specification	Year											Change from 2011 in 2021, +/-
	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	
GDP	61,9	60,8	60,9	61,9	64,6	66,8	65,3	62,4	56,0	55,7	54,9	-7,0
Industry	28,6	29,7	33,0	36,8	40,6	45,3	41,2	37,4	25,8	27,9	27,0	-1,6
Construction	67,6	70,0	70,6	69,5	66,7	66,9	64,8	73,2	75,8	72,5	72,4	4,8
Employment	75,1	75,6	76,7	77,6	77,9	78,2	78,0	76,3	76,2	74,5	74,4	-0,7
Export	18,8	14,0	26,2	27,0	27,0	26,0	22,0	27,2	27,0	20,5	22,3	3,5
Import	34,3	38,6	42,4	45,4	44,5	46,8	53,6	56,2	61,6	51,7	48,7	14,4

In industrial sectors, however, it can be seen that the increase in the amount of business entities is going much more sluggish compared to the agricultural sector, depending on the production conditions and characteristics in the sector. If a total of 16,627 units of small business entities operated on the network in 2013, by 2021 the number had grown to 45,897 units. In other words, the number of small business entities operating in industrial sectors is almost 10 times less than in agricultural sectors. The state of rapid growth in the number of business entities is very actively growing in the field of transportation and storage services as a result of the sharp development of the service sector. In this area, a total of 57,376 units of business

entities were active in 2013, while at the end of 2021 their number reached 156,539 units, or in other words, the change was about 3 times.

Table 3.

Number of small business entities operating in the cross section of economic sectors, Unit[3]

Specification	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Village, forest and fish farming	189867	196014	207104	210594	229666	262930	334767	411203	462834
Industry	16627	16739	17357	17962	20530	23975	28847	40719	45897
Construction	36128	38977	41066	42847	48566	56233	69970	82746	90313
Trade	18374	19616	20863	21790	23807	28955	36021	40695	43410
Transportation and storage	57376	57690	58930	61214	62714	70457	100573	131597	156539
Living and catering services	7813	8486	9488	10631	11779	13121	15157	17056	18045
Information and communication	11905	12969	14194	15293	16964	19656	25461	29947	32948
Health and social services	6396	6443	6327	6201	6167	6738	7621	9221	10247
Other areas	5755	5695	5772	3709	4417	5364	6370	7588	8814

An analysis of the number of small business entities in the cross section of the territories of our country makes it possible to more accurately see in which regions of this type of activity is actively developing or, in other words, which territory or region is developing on the basis of small business. From the statistics of the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, consisting of timed rows covering the period from 2013 to 2021, we will try to analyze the level of development of small business entities operating in our country in the cross-section of Regions (Table 4).

The table data shows that the number of small business entities by the regions of our country has grown more than 5 times over the past 9 years, that is, a total of 189867 units of small business entities operated in 2013, while at the end of 2021 their number was 462834 units.

In terms of the number of small business entities operating in our country, the regions of Tashkent, Tashkent, Samarkand, Fergana, Andijan and Kashkadarya have a high rate, while the regions of Syrdarya, Jizzakh and the Republic of Karakalpakstan have a much lower than average level of the country.

Table 4

Number of small business entities operating in the cross section of Regions, Unit[3]

Regions	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
The.	189867	196014	207104	210594	229666	262930	334767	411203	462834
Republic Of Karakalpakstan	8383	9327	9642	9638	10539	11985	14677	18288	19998
Andijan	19966	20872	21982	21713	20342	22560	25807	31683	34999
Bukhara	8724	9386	11141	11615	12648	14805	19981	24809	27690
Jizzakh	7183	7505	7881	8013	9310	11197	14011	17725	19463
Caloptilia	16087	15808	14870	13785	14347	16218	20304	25297	31152
Navoi	6219	6309	6728	6731	7569	9104	14885	17931	20472
Namangan	12292	13080	14094	14667	15949	16975	21461	26531	28949
Samarkand	12648	12860	13840	13981	16005	19629	25643	33114	40724
Surkhandarya	10590	9062	9061	9418	10409	11618	15509	21563	24395
Syrdarya	6143	6403	6499	6954	7462	8318	11026	13360	13808
Tashkent	17848	19009	19546	19458	21647	25410	32602	40223	44156
Fergana	16113	16920	18108	17802	20225	23304	29300	36117	40403
Khwarazm	9911	10393	10298	10384	10900	11815	15453	18875	21984
Tashkent City	37760	39080	43414	46435	52314	59992	74108	85687	94641

In particular, the number of small business entities operating in the city of Tashkent has grown more than 2.5 times over the past 9 years. If in 2013 the number of small business entities operating in the area was 37,760 units, by the end of 2021 the number was 94,641 units. This figure increased from 17848 units in Tashkent region to 44156 units in Samaraqand region, from 12648 units to 40724 units (3.5 times) in Fergana region, from 16113 units to 44156 units in Fergana region, from 19966 units to 34999 units in Andijan region, respectively.

And in the Republic of Syrdarya, Jizzakh regions and Karakalpakstan, we can see that the number of small business entities is developing in the regions in proportion to the number of economically active residents available.

The number of small businesses operating in Syrdarya region was 6,143 units in 2013 with 13,808 units in 2021. These indicators increased by years from 7183 units in Jizzakh region to 19463 units, respectively, and in the Republic of Karakalpakstan from 8383 units to 19998 units. While the number of small business entities operating in these areas has increased to a perceived level over a period of 9 years, the areas remain among the lowest ranked by country in terms of quantity. Analysis of certain indicators in the labor market by country also makes it possible to more accurately analyze the development of small-scale entrepreneurial activity in our country (Table 5).

Table 5

The share of small business entities in creating new jobs in Uzbekistan, a thousand people [3]

Specification name	2015	2017	2018	2019	2020
Newly created jobs	940,5	950,0	956,2	973,5	960,0
including:					
In small business and private entrepreneurship	391,8	480,0	600,1	602,2	480,0
In percentage account	41,7	50,5	62,8	61,9	50,0
The proportion of people employed in small business and private entrepreneurship in relation to the total number of people employed in the economy, in percentage accounting	74,2	74,4	74,8	75,0	76,5

The table shows that in the next period, when about 1 million new jobs are being created in our country per year, more than half of them are in the field of small entrepreneurship and private entrepreneurship.

In 2020, more than 680,000 new jobs were created in the field of small entrepreneurship and private entrepreneurship. This means half of the total jobs created. Today, more than 76.5% of the working population is working in this area

of the economy. In 2015, the rate was 49.7 percent . This suggests that the small business sector plays an important role in solving the problem of employment and the organization of new jobs.

In our republic, it is envisaged to support small-scale entrepreneurship in every possible way, making them a solid economic sector that can compete in the domestic and foreign markets, and consistently manage the production of quality products and the provision of services. An important place is occupied by the creation of a favorable business environment in the full-fledged development of entrepreneurship, which constitutes an important sector of the national economy.

Through these measures, the radical reduction of the intervention of state and control bodies in the financial and economic activities of enterprises, the further improvement of the system for organizing inspections, the provision of strengthening the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of business entities on this basis contributed to the acceleration of socio-economic development of our country, the provision of

In order to radically increase the role and role of private property in the economy of the Republic, eliminate obstacles and restrictions on the development of private property and private entrepreneurship, reduce state participation in the economy, consistently increase the share of private property in the gross domestic product, including foreign capital, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to ensure reliable protection of Private Property, Small-the son decree was adopted. The decree approved a program of measures to ensure reliable protection of private property, small business and private entrepreneurship, to eliminate obstacles to their rapid development.

Also, from July 1, 2019, individual entrepreneurs, depending on their activities, were given the right to hire from one to three employees, provided that they pay an insurance contribution of 50% of the minimum monthly salary to the extra-budgetary pension fund for each hired employee and a strictly defined tax of

30% of the established rate for the individual employer entrepreneur.

Individual entrepreneurs were exempted from a strictly defined tax on hired workers within twelve months of graduating from college in the case of hiring professional college graduates.

From all of the above, special attention is paid to the use of the opportunities of small-scale entrepreneurial and entrepreneurial activity in improving the well-being of the population in Uzbekistan. In particular, the various tax benefits given to our entrepreneurs, the simplification of registration, reporting, the assistance of the state through various privileges in the implementation of export operations, the sharp extension of the deadlines for the transfer of entrepreneurs' activities from control, etc. provide wide opportunities for domestic and foreign entrepreneurs operating in our country, and as a result of the rational policy

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